

Getting Started and Running the Experiments

We have included a virtual machine on Zenodo (DOI:10.5281/zenodo.5915048) that is setup with all the necessary tools and libraries to run our experiment. (Virtual machine requirements are listed in the requirement section.) The virtual machine has both the username and password of “sugarc”.

The virtual machine has scripts to run all three of our target real-world programs (axtls, toybox, and busybox) in Section 5.3 as well as our DesugarBench microbenchmark in Section 5.2. The script to run DesugarBench also runs and compares both prior works, Hercules and CReconfigurator. All scripts are located in, and should be run from, the “/home/sugarc/”, or “~/” directory of the virtual machine.

All files printed in the scripts aimed at our test projects are marked with a status, one of ignoring, successful, not compiling, or not desugaring. The labels have the following meanings:

- Successful - the output produced by the SugarC compiles with no errors.
- Not Compiling - an output is produced, but compiling with gcc produces errors.
- Not Desugaring - an output is not able to be produced for one reason or another
- Ignoring - The file is problematic, either taking up extremely large amounts of time, or memory. This is also where files may be placed if they are known to have syntax not currently supported by SugarC.

The scripts are as follows:

- RunDesugarBench.sh

```
$bash RunDesugarBench.sh
```

This script runs SugarC, Hercules, and Creconfigurator on all tests in the microbenchmark. The output files are placed in “/tmp/sugarc”, “/tmp/Hercules”, and “/tmp/creconfig” respectively. These folders have the same structure as the DesugarBench test cases (found in:

“/home/sugarc/sugarc/fonda/cpp_testsuite/desugarer/microbenchmark/testcases”)

- Note: the results of this benchmark are solely if the output compiles, or identifies an error. The results don’t include the manual investigation.
- Note: Creconfigurator was run with 64gb of RAM in our actual evaluation. This virtual machine is only configured with 16gb of RAM, this might lead to slight discrepancies. If you would like to change this, you can edit the file “/home/sugarc/sugarc/fonda/cpp_testsuite/desugarer/microbenchmark/tools/creconfigurator/creconfigurator.config” and increasing the value of javaXmx to 64g. You will also have to increase the RAM allowed to the virtual machine.
- This script should complete in a matter of minutes

Sample output:

test type	Hercules	creconfigurator	sugarC
control_flow_statements	5 / 6	3 / 6	6 / 6
variadic_arguments	3 / 4	2 / 4	4 / 4
ANSI	6 / 7	6 / 7	7 / 7
K&R	3 / 6	6 / 6	1 / 6
struct_union_enum_specifiers	12 / 16	14 / 16	16 / 16
typedef_declarations_specifiers	4 / 5	4 / 5	5 / 5
basic_declarators	13 / 18	14 / 18	18 / 18
identifier_and_function_call	8 / 10	6 / 10	9 / 10
unary_binary_ternary	6 / 7	4 / 7	7 / 7
external_declarations	4 / 4	4 / 4	4 / 4
syntactic_error_integration	1 / 4	3 / 4	4 / 4
semantic_error_integration	0 / 21	6 / 21	21 / 21

- RunAxtls.sh

```
$bash RunAxtls.sh
```

This script runs SugarC on all of the .c files in the “SystemConfig/axtls/” directory and sub-directories. After processing each file, the results are written to “SystemConfig/axtlsRes.txt”, the RunAxtls.sh file also prints these results.

- Note: c files under the “SystemConfig/axtls/axtls-code/scripts” directory were not explored or included in any results, despite the fact that the script executes them.
- Given the default specifications, this script should run for roughly 55-75 minutes.

Sample output:

```
ignoring:0/43
successful:31/43
not compiling:0/43
not desugaring:12/43
```

- RunToybox.sh

```
$bash RunToybox.sh
```

This script runs SugarC on all of the .c files in the “SystemConfig/toybox-0.7.5/” directory and sub-directories. After processing each file, the results are written to “SystemConfig/toyboxRes.txt”, the RunToybox.sh file also prints these results.

- Note: c files outside of the “SystemConfig/toybox-0.7.5/toys” directory were not explored or included in any results, despite the fact that the script executes them.
- Note: Due to the limited processing power, we find that the virtual machine takes a very long amount of time to execute each file in toybox. To fix this, we have limited the configuration options by defaulting more to false. This does not affect

the success of any file we included in our tests, but it does make the outputs smaller. The original file used in our experiments is also included if needed, you may switch to these by running the command:

```
$mv SystemConfig/toyboxInc.h SystemConfig/toyboxIncNew.h; mv SystemConfig/toyboxIncOriginal.h SystemConfig/toyboxInc.h
```

And it can be reverted with the following command:

```
$mv SystemConfig/toyboxInc.h SystemConfig/toyboxIncOriginal.h; mv SystemConfig/toyboxIncNew.h SystemConfig/toyboxInc.h
```

- **Warning:** While toybox does execute, due to single threading and limited processing power running toybox takes a very long time. These limitations don't allow us to confirm that our virtual machine will have the exact same results. The first file to execute, main.c, is not included in the experiment and takes a particularly long time to execute. While it is running, you may use the command "Ctrl+C" to cancel it. Later we discuss SingleToybox.sh, which can be used to run individual files for testing.
- RunBusybox.sh

```
$bash RunBusybox.sh
```

This script runs SugarC on all .c files that are built while building busybox (Which is found in "SystemConfig/busybox-1.28.0"). The results of which are stored in a json file "SystemConfig/busybox-1.28.0/files.json". RunBusybox.sh will also print the results.

- **Warning:** While busybox does execute, due to single threading and limited processing power running busybox takes a very long time. These limitations don't allow us to confirm that our virtual machine will have the exact same results. Later we discuss SingleBusybox.sh, which can be used to run individual files for testing.
- SingleToybox.sh && SingleBusybox.sh

```
$bash SingleToybox.sh toys/other/mix.c
```

```
$bash SingleBusybox.sh libbb/getopt32.c
```

Since Busybox and Toybox take a long time to run, these scripts allow the running of a single file, provided through a command line argument. The file used must be exact, given the relative directory from "/home/sugarc/SystemConfig/toybox-0.7.5/" or "/home/sugarc/SystemConfig/busybox-1.28.0/" respectively.

Sample outputs:
SingleToybox.sh:

```
/home/sugarc/SystemConfig/toybox-0.7.5/toys/other/mix.c:successful 44 1817 981607
1024
ignoring:0/1
successful:1/1
not compiling:0/1
not desugaring:0/1
```

The four numbers are as follows time of execution in seconds, size of the file in bytes, size of the desugared output in bytes, the number of static conditionals. Time of execution will always vary, for estimations check the desugared results from the spreadsheet.

SingleBusybox.sh

```
libbb/getopt32.c: successful
```

For busybox, only the results of the file are printed.

- cleanup.sh

```
$bash cleanup.sh
```

This removes almost all of the files created by RunAxtls.sh, RunToybox.sh, and RunBusybox.sh. This includes the clang analysis results, Log files, desugared files, and object files created when a desugared file compiles successfully.

Note: there is no output from cleanup.sh

Running SugarC Outside of Scripts:

SugarC is built and ready to run on the virtual machine. To run it on any given file (for example, a file named sample.c) you would execute the following command.

```
$java superc.SugarC sample.c
```

If you would like to see a list of commands you can use to change execution use the following command.

```
$java superc.SugarC
```

Output that occurs during execution is output through the error pipeline, where only the desugared output is output through the standard pipeline. With this you can easily redirect different parts of the process to different files. In our experiment we use “> sample.desugared.c” to place the our desugared results in a runnable file, and “2> sample.Log” which we used during testing to identify bugs.

Other Notes:

- All of our test projects were run with between 4 to 10 threads in parallel. Due to the limitations of the virtual machines, the tests all execute with just one thread. If you wish to enhance the specs of the virtual machine and run these in parallel, the variable named “parallel” at the top of “SystemConfig/axtIsRunner.py”, “SystemConfig/toybox-0.7.5/toyboxRunner.py” and

“SystemConfig/busybox-1.28.0/busyboxRunner.py” can be edited. The value is the number of concurrent threads.